

STORABLE NEWSLETTER

Dear reader,

We welcome the new year with the first STORABLE newsletter. We are very proud to present this cluster, currently comprising the Horizon 2020 project NeoGiANT, three doctoral networks (two of which are Europe Horizon MSCA DNs), four private companies, and two research groups/projects.

STORABLE (Semen sTORage for sustAinaBle animal brEeding) aims at creating a forum for sharing, disseminating, and discussing knowledge related to sustainability in animal reproduction, especially regarding antimicrobial resistance and antibiotic replacement. This cluster is one of the results of the NeoGiANT project (<https://www.neogiant.eu>; Horizon 2020, 101036768) and aims to foster **collaboration** among partners while **disseminating** knowledge on sustainable strategies in animal breeding.

CONEREPRO

HeteroBull

Precisión Celular

BULLNET

ANDROEXPERT

Topigs Norsvin

PROGRESS IN PIGS

AIM Ibérica

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STORABLE was promoted by **NeoGiANT's work package 6**, dedicated to animal reproduction (<https://www.neogiant.eu/work-packages/>), including groups from the University of South Bohemia and the Veterinary Research Institute in the Czech Republic, and the private companies Bianor Biotech SL and Magapor SL in Spain.

STORABLE first activities and kick-off meeting

STORABLE started its activities in 2025 with in-person meetings at Magapor's ITM congress in May and the European Association for Embryo Transfer congress in September.

These were excellent opportunities to get to know each other and to plan the cluster's objectives and roadmap.

We celebrated the official kickoff meeting with an online event in October, which was a great success and included presentations from each partner.

First webinar

We held our first webinar on December 17th on the topic "The challenge of antimicrobial resistance and innovative approaches for semen storage." **Dr. Óscar Mencía** from the University of León (Spain) delivered an excellent presentation on the impact of antimicrobial resistance in swine production, with an overview of great interest to the cluster.

Approaches to studying antimicrobial resistance

Methods for the detection of antimicrobial resistance

Phenotypic methods

- Disk diffusion (Kirby-Bauer)
- Broth microdilution

Genotypic approaches

- Detection of resistance determinants by PCR
- Sequencing-based approaches:
 - Whole genome sequencing (WGS)
 - Metagenomics

Dr. Jane Morrell (SLU, Sweden) presented the latest advances on the application of single-layer centrifugation and hypothermic storage of boar semen as an alternative to antibiotics in semen

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extenders. Finally, **Dr. Aleksandar Cojkic** (SLU) showed his research on bull semen, including evaluations of the semen microbiome and alternatives to antibiotics in semen extenders.

This event was a great success, with 65 attendants, including guests from other organizations.

Next steps

STORABLE aims to hold its next webinar in March-April, focusing on sustainable strategies in animal breeding. This activity focuses on first-stage researchers from the different partners, especially PhD candidates and early postdocs.

UPCOMING EVENTS

We encourage these young researchers to deliver a short presentation, followed by a debate. This activity is not only an excellent opportunity to present and debate, but also to learn about the research

lines of the different groups and to identify opportunities for collaboration.

Acknowledgements and contacts

The coordinators warmly thank all the partners for their excellent disposition. We include the NeoGiANT project, the Horizon 2020 program, and the Booster program from Horizon Europe for their support.

If you want to know more about STORABLE's partners or contact them, you can find them at:

- <https://bianorbiotech.es/>
- <https://www.jcu.cz/en/>
- <https://www.vri.cz/en/900-2/>
- <https://magapor.com/>
- <https://www.ul.ie/research/bullnet-research>
- <https://precisioncelular.com/>
- <https://www.cryostoreproject.com/>
- <https://semencardona.com/>
- <https://veterinaria.ucm.es/conerepro>
- <https://aimiberica.com/>
- <https://topigsnorsvin.com/>
- <https://www.inia.es/en-en/Research/Animalresearch/animalreproduction/Spermatology%20in%20Animal%20Production%20and%20Conservation/Paginas/Home.aspx>

You can follow STORABLE's news and activities at [LinkedIn](#), [Bluesky](#), and [Mastodon](#).